

Hotel Occupancy Management for the Sustainability of the Sucre-San Vicente Destination from the Perspective of a Tourist Circuit

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ABSTRACT: The objective of this research is to design a tourist circuit that allows increasing the arrival of national and international tourists, raising the occupancy rates of hotels and contributing to the tourist development of Sucre and San Vicente cantons. The research methodology was descriptive, using qualitative and quantitative methods. The tools used were: The documentary review, Kendall coefficient method and diagram cause effect. As a result of the research of different expert authors in tourism, it was possible to obtain a form that facilitates the creation of touristic circuits that allow increasing the arrival of national and international tourists, raise the percentages of occupancy of the hotels and contribute to the development of the tourist destination. The elaborated mode was in correspondence with the bibliographical revision, in addition it contains the current tendencies of the state of the art and of the practice. The diagnosis of the hotel capacity and study of the attractions allowed to make a proposal of sustainable tourist circuits.

Keywords: Management, tourist circuit, occupation, sustainability

I. INTRODUCTION

Palaces A, (2012) bases that tourism is an activity carried out by people who move from a place different from their habitual residence and by a motivation that is the one that directs them to the activity that they will fulfill in the place who have decided that they are going to visit. The idea of tourism was increasing with the development of humanity with the passage of time the activity was more common within the activities and due to that the options within the tourist field worldwide are several, you can go to different places of leisure and also to places where tourists can self educate themselves.

Cervantes J. A, (2017) instead argues that currently, it must be recognized that excellence in customer service as a fundamental factor for the growth of the tourism sector, the same that, within Ecuador has been developed and Year after year seeks to increase international quality standards within the processes and activities carried out. The tourism sector is an inexhaustible source of economic growth, in addition to permanently promoting service within society, seeks quality in all its areas, as well as competitiveness with other destinations worldwide.

Neide L, (2017) in its study pursues the objective of characterizing the development processes of community tourism in the Brazilian Northeast, taking as references experiences in Brazil and secondary sources that complement the analysis of the benefits of tourism for local communities, such as also understandings about community tourism. Where it also bases the importance and the role of governments, they generally position themselves in favor of these transnational hotel enterprises and facilitate whatever is necessary to guarantee the attraction of foreign capital, ensuring the basic infrastructure of urban services related to urban transport, communications, drinking water supply, paving, sewerage, etc. They start from the premise that these ventures are the engines of development

According to Echarri M, (2015), it is based on his research that the participation of municipal authorities, service providers and the community in general is essential to obtain benefits from tourism. From this reality, a considerable number of the products and services demanded by tourism come from other places; that is, they are not generated in the territory where the tourist activity takes place. This diversity of activities favors the exchange and a more balanced regional development.

Triana R, Barrios F & Rúa S, (2017) bases that within the main challenges that the development of the tourist sector has, is the need to be objective at the time of identifying the resources in terms of attractiveness that make up the offer for develop competitive products; involving the rurality of the territory and establishing criteria of sustainability as a transversal axis of the new economies and in response to increasingly specialized markets. In this way, try to approximate when establishing the relationship between tourism and territory; that incorporates the characteristics that allow the conditions of thinking typologies such as nature with landscapes of water and culture through historical memory; paying attention to the function of resources, their classification, conditions and designated treatment.

Ecuador through the Ministry of Tourism makes available to local governments, organizations, tourism industry and citizens in general a toolbox to strengthen tourism management by promoting innovation in products, services, destinations and projects with the purpose of increasing and enhancing the development of tourism in the country.

Creating a touristic circuit within the Sucre and San Vicente cantons is part of the management as an element to promote tourist activity in the destination, being of utmost importance to establish an economic development in the communities, in the same way it helps to stimulate the activities tourist activities that take place within them.

Cervantes A, (2015) argues that tourism is understood as "that tourist route with return to the same place, without going through the same place twice." There is a growing interest in tourist circuits, due to human curiosity to know other regions, its human and cultural heritage is one of the most sought after tourism experiences by the desire of tourists to have authentic experiences typical of the fate of the local community

In the same way there are tourist routes which is a touristic route in a straight line to different ends with the option of passing twice through the same place, without returning to the point of departure, very different from the circuits which is characterized for being circulate and arrive at the same place of departure.

León, (2017) Minister of Tourism in Ecuador quotes in the newspaper Commerce that one of the goals is to make a single tourist circuit in Ecuador, establishing agreements between entrepreneurs, investors and other actors to strengthen this

sector. In his proposal, he has two defined lines of work: the creation and promotion of travel packages to travel the country, and the impulse of what he calls "1x1 tourist" that is, one tourist per inhabitant, explained the minister Ecuatoriano de Tourism,

Prior to arguments we know that a tourist circuit depends on sociocultural and economic factors existing in the communities or localities of the country, which in turn are integrated by all the resources and tourist attractions that these cantons have, giving them an opportune use of them. Through the existing statistical sources of information gathering already structured within the cantons, a diagnosis or analysis of them is facilitated, thus allowing to design new tourist circuits.

According to author Vera, J.F, (2012) tourism in spaces of high environmental value is not a recent phenomenon. The novelty is that for some decades, that desire to know the natural spaces or to carry out recreational activities in them has been generalized among the social mass, becoming one of the motivations for the trip of greater growth.

The result is visible which benefits the different cities that are recognized worldwide for their excellence in quality of services and the different attractions that make them unique for tourists, is that they are incorporated into the demand of destinations and tourist peripheries each they are more distant from the spaces themselves and at the same time that the motivations become more varied and, linked to them, new more specialized specific tourist products that satisfy the needs of tourists are emerging.

The author Cervantes A, (2015) considers the performance of the tourist operator or designer in the preparation of tourist circuits is a combination of information previously acquired both theoretical and practical, that is, should be designed from the observation and experience gained during the transfer to the different points that will make up the tourist circuit, but there must also be compilation of statistical data, approximate costs of each route, strategic stopping points and other elements that point with great precision. The designer then has to carefully study all the information in order to highlight or choose the most important aspects of the design in question. Each of the phases that make up the design merit dedication and particular study, to go together harmoniously.

Therefore "Tourist Circuit is a set of territorial spaces that form the same offer of tourism goods and services." It is a circular or semicircular route that starts from a transmitter or receiver center and that has attractions and facilities along its route. It is also understood by tourist circuit "that tourist route with return to the same place without going through the same place twice". (Tourism, 2010)

It is also notorious to consider hotel occupancy, which as Sandoval author (2012) states, the hotel industry encompasses all those establishments dedicated to providing a lodging and food service to permanent guests or passers-by. This industry also includes activities that are carried out jointly or in relation to the exploitation of this type of company. In addition, within this industry we can find those establishments that are dedicated to hospedería with few rooms, those that provide accommodation for specially instructive purposes or medical assistance, and student accommodation. As we can see the hotel industry is quite broad. However, a central aspect of this industry is represented by tourist attractions, which in turn are related to the ease of the place, infrastructure, transportation.

It is worth mentioning that the tourism deficit in the canton and the poor level of occupancy of the hotel facilities are mainly due to the lack of tourist circuits that manage the destination of Sucre and San Vicente cantons. That in turn this circuit integrates the attractions and natural resources existing in the localities and communities, allowing logar an occupancy level above 30%, that overnight stay overnight by cantons, in addition to the low levels of efficiency in tourist services based on the basic indicators that it manages and the overall efficiency index of the sector, as well as the low levels of efficiency in tourism services based on the basic indicators it manages and the overall efficiency index of the sector, among other deficiencies.

It is important to emphasize that after the stagnation experienced in the last 3 years, the arrival figures of foreign tourists to the country are encouraging, because according to preliminary data, in 2017 there were 1'617.914 tourists, representing a growth of 14% with respect to 2016. This is indicated by the information provided by the General Coordination of Statistics and Research of MINTUR, which in its report highlights that only in December 2017 was recorded the largest increase in arrivals in the year, that is, a growth of 30, 3% higher than in December 2016 when it received 171,926 foreigners who visited the different tourist destinations in the country. (MINTUR, 2018)

The objective pursued by this study is to design a circuit that manages the tourist destination of the Sucre San Vicente cantons, which allows from the management to increase the arrival of national and international tourists, also raise the percentages of occupancy of hotels and contribute to sustainable development of tourism in the destination.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The descriptive method will allow an analysis of the research problem. Qualitative and quantitative methods are used for the diagnosis. The population sample obtained was in accordance with the tourists who occupied the hotel floor during the carnival holiday time in the canton, but a non-probabilistic sampling is practiced for convenience, therefore there is no need to perform a sample size calculation and 60 surveys were carried out. .

It should be noted that in order to obtain the sample of the research, a group of people will be chosen at random, thus conducting the survey, as well as an interview with an expert on topics related to tourist circuits that contribute empirical knowledge to research. .

Developing in this way methods that allow the construction of the scientific theory, as well as to deepen in the knowledge of the regularities and essential qualities of the phenomena. According to the author Ibarra C, (2011) "They fulfill an important gnoseological function, since they allow us to interpret the empirical data found in the concept".

In this way, the empirical method that will be developed in the research takes shape, such as the method of observation, which is one of the methods that will be used to determine the results of surveys and the probability of raising a natural, cultural or tourist resource. short-term history. As the author Cortez Y affirms, (2013) "Scientific observation as a method consists in the direct preparation of the object of the research, the researched observation is the universal instrument of the scientist, allows to know reality through the direct perception of objects and phenomena "

Similarly the author Herrera V, (2013) argues that observation is a process of attention, collection and recording of information, for which the researcher relies on their senses (sight, smell, hearing, touch, smell, kinesthetic and kinesthetic senses) .In the observation, elements such as recording instruments (the senses) or mechanical instruments (video cameras, tape measure, etc.) intervene.

The population considered in this case study were random tourists from the Sucre and San Vicente cantons located in the headwaters of the city of Bahía de Caráquez and San Vicente Ciudad. The sampling applied was the non-probabilistic one that does not require calculation of the sample size. Considering the foregoing, 60 surveys were applied to tourists from the identified geographical area.

The Kendall Method will be applied in order to unify the criteria of a group of specialists, with knowledge of the subject under study. Qualified personnel are selected, with experience in that work. Each member of the panel weighs according to the order of importance that each one understands at their discretion ascending or descending the characteristics. The expert number should be between 7 and 15. It is important to take into account that an expert does not mean professional, but a broad expert on the subject and clearly explain to them the objectives that we pursue with the study or investigation and the importance of their impartiality.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The procedure that will be implemented for the design of the tourist circuit is based on the lines of (Cervantes A., 2015) in which it affirms that the performance of the tourist operator or designer in the elaboration of tourist circuits is a combination of previously acquired information. theoretical as a practice, that is, they should be designed based on the observation and experience obtained during the transfer to the different points that will make up the tourist circuit, but there should also be statistical data collection, approximate costs of each route, strategic stopping points and other elements that point with great precision.

It is important to note that the creation of the tourist circuit is in accordance with the technique expressed by the author Cervantes A (2015). That makes mention of what is essential to create the circuit. It is worth mentioning that this circuit crosses the cities of Bahía de Caráquez and San Vicente Ciudad, which does not include the parish of Charapoto, surrounding areas and San Isidro parish, so that more than 80% of tourists arrive at the destination Sucre - San Vicente comes from Quito and it is more feasible to make the circuit in this way. The circuit "The Cities of the Sun" express gastronomy, sun and beach, landscaping.

The objective of this survey was to identify the problems that affect the low influx of tourists in the Cantones Sucre and San Vicente hotels. It was applied to the residents and tourists of the Sucre and San Vicente cantons, which turned out to be a total of 60 people. The instrument was based on 5 questions that contribute to the development of a tourist circuit in the study area.

IV. DIAGNOSIS OF THE HOTEL PLANT.

Hotel sustainability is the result of teamwork, which will be entrusted to the owner of the accommodation, and covers both the social, cultural and environmental development of their management, as they provide greater confidence and empathy in the guests. It also shows general advantages that allow improving the corporate image, to increase the level of loyalty by customers and economic demand. Below is a statistics of hotel capacity in the canton of Sucre, which is the least representative and most affected by the 2016 earthquake.

Table 1: Hotel plant occupancy level

Categoría	N° Categoría	Número de habitaciones	Porcentaje de habitaciones	Porcentaje de habitaciones	Capacidad de clientes	Porcentaje de capacidad
Hotel	4	18%	61	22%	194	19%
Hostal	4	18%	63	22%	207	21%
Hostal Residencial	4	18%	64	23%	222	22%
Hostería	3	14%	19	7%	95	10%
Pensión	5	23%	62	22%	207	21%
Cabaña	2	9%	13	5%	70	7%
Total	22	100%	282	100%	995	100%

Source: Cadastre 2017

It is shown in table 1 that the most representative number of hotel facilities turned out to be the so-called pensions with 23%, followed by Hotels, Hostels and Residential Hostels with 18% each, Hostelries in 14% and Cabañas in 9% . According to the capacity of clients, the establishments with the highest percentage are Residential Hostels with 22%, Hostels and Pensions represented 21% each, Hotels 19% followed by Inns 10% and with 7% cabins, these lodges currently by their occupation can be taken over in the hotel market in Canton Sucre.

Study carried out on the occupation in the hotel companies in San Vicente canton shows a lower number of representativeness of services, even so it has a recognition in the tourist market at a regional, national and international level. Table 2 shows a statistical survey at the category level of the hotels in this destination.

Table 2: Hotel Services of the San Vicente Canton

Categoría	N° Categoría	% por Categoría	N° Habitaciones	% de Habitaciones	N° de Plaza	% de Plaza
Hotel	4	24%	20	5%	100	10%
Hostal	3	18%	139	36%	252	26%
Hostal Residencial	2	12%	43	11%	81	8%
Hostería	3	18%	30	8%	100	10%
Pensión	3	18%	103	27%	220	23%
Cabaña	2	12%	52	13%	214	22%
Total	17	100%	387	100%	967	100%

Prepared by: authors

Hotel Occupancy Management for the Sustainability of the Sucre-San Vicente Destination from the

In this stage, according to the results obtained, it was determined that after the earthquake there were a greater number of hotels with 24%, followed by Hostels and Hostels and Pensions with 18% each, Hostel of Residence and Cabins by 12% . According to the capacity of clients, the establishments with the highest percentage of rooms are the Hostels with 36%, followed by the Pensions with 27%, the Hotels with 19%, the Cabins with 13%, followed by the Residential Hostels in 11%, and also with a low percentage are the Hostelries with 8% and with 5% the hotels, these accommodations currently because of their occupation are owned in the hotel market in the San Vicente Canton.

In this canton, the percentage of hotel services is too low due to the natural disaster of 16A, which caused it to be the most affected in the tourism sector, since 70% of its infrastructure was collapsed, the facilities that are currently located are those that find more sections of downtown Canton.

1.1 Implementation of the Kendall coefficient method

Seven experts with more than 10 years of experience in tourism management were selected and, applying the Kendall coefficient method, 11 faults were obtained from Sucre and San Vicente cantons.

- Lack of knowledge of tourism management by public officials and hotel managers.
- Inadequate price quality ratio, high prices are charged for products that do not guarantee quality.
- The offer in the hotels lacks the essential services of the hotel, only accommodation is provided and not gastronomy or entertainment.
- The maintenance and conservation of the attractions is deficient.
- There are no tourist attractions of category 3 and 4 that can provide the arrival of national and international tourists.
- Divorce between public and private companies.
- There are no tourist tour operators in these cantons that are capable of designing tourism products.
- There is no culture of services, the borrowers are not trained or the managers in customer service techniques.
- Polluted beaches that do not meet safety requirements.
- Little environmental, hygienic culture in the community which affects the landscapes of these cantons.

Table 3: Kendall coefficient

Eventos	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	$\sum i$	$\sum i - T$	
									Δ	Δ^2
1	1	2	1	2	3	3	2	14	28	784
2	11	10	11	9	10	11	10	71	29	841
3	10	11	10	10	11	10	11	73	31	961
4	9	9	9	11	9	9	9	65	23	529
5	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	11	31	961
6	3	3	4	3	1	1	3	18	24	576
7	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	27	15	225
8	5	5	6	5	6	5	5	37	5	25
9	6	7	5	6	5	6	6	40	2	4
10	7	6	7	8	7	8	7	50	8	64
11	8	8	8	7	8	7	8	54	12	144
Total								$\sum \sum i = 460$		$\sum = 5114$
								$T = 460/11 = 42$		

Formula to validate the study with the experts, and verify if the proposed proposal is valid or not

$$W = \frac{12 \sum \Delta^2}{m^2 (k^3 - k)}$$

$$\geq 0,5 \text{ esValido}$$

M =Number of Experts (7)

K=Number of Events (11)

E=Experts

Δ = Delta

T=Comparison factor

W=Coefficient of agreement

$$W = \frac{12 \times 5114}{49 (1331 - 11)}$$

$$W = \frac{61.368}{49 (1320)}$$

$$W = 64.680$$

$$W = 0,94 \geq 0,5 \text{ (The concordance coefficient study is Valid).}$$

According to results of the Kendall Method, these are the main factors that affect the low influx of tourists within the Sucre and San Vicente cantons.

DESIGN OF THE TOURIST CIRCUIT "THE CITIES OF THE SUN".

The tourist circuit "The Cities of the Sun" in its greatest splendor, will have the opportunity to visit the cities and their tourist attractions, the purpose is to highlight the tourist attractions within these cantons, which over time have been deteriorating or have little reception at local, national and international level. In the same way highlight new tourism resources, which by administering them in a good way will launch new tourism products, increasing the flow of visitors

The purpose of this work is to reflect on changes in tourism trends, making an analysis of the launch of a new tourism product whose aim is to achieve sustainable development at the environmental, tourism and social levels through the generation of employment and the supply of products sun and beach tourism.

It should be noted that the cantons that are delimited in the northern area of Manabí, are not promoted, nor is it provided with the necessary audiovisual information of the established tourist attractions and will provide a

contribution to those destinations not yet exploited, so that they can be known by medium of strategies allowing to learn a little more about the different attractions and history that the town has.

The tourist circuit will have a tour within these two cantons highlighting the main points or the most relevant attractions of the town, making a guide for the different places that will be established in strategically shaped parts for the long stay or a journey of hours of travel that starts in the city of San Vicente.

We must take into account the option to capture this circuit during periods of the year where you can make different tourist activities depending on the weather station you are in, thus highlighting other tourist resources that are not very relevant in this area as hiking, hiking, camping, among others, which would contribute to socio-economic development as well as environmental management.

According to the strategic plan of Cantonal Tourism Development of Sucre and San Vicente, the first manifestations of tourism occurred in the 19th century when Bahía de Caráquez was considered one of the most important ports in the country and received visitors from different parts of the world for reasons mainly business. In the mid-nineteenth century, the first hotels to offer services in that denomination were the Hotel Americano and the Vesuvius Hotel. In San Jacinto, San Clemente, San Vicente, Canoa hotels began to appear in the early 70's, the residential San Clemente was the first that I appreciate with a commercial name for tourism purposes. (Sucre, 2013)

1. Implementation activities within the tourist circuit

Four objectives were proposed to be able to comply with the implementation of the tourist circuit in order that this project is a contribution to the historical, cultural, natural, religious tourism, etc. Evaluating the investigations and the fulfillment of the proposed activities, it is determined that the information gathering process will help to clearly propose a novel product to encourage tourism in the northern area of the Sucre and San Vicente cantons.

This is a strategy that allows attracting all types of tourists whether national or foreign, evoking the aforementioned that "there is a growing interest in tourist circuits", therefore the focus of this idea is to bring tourists from other regions or from other countries making them visit the town for the interest of new tourist routes, making detailed knowledge of our history, culture, gastronomy, as well as natural and cultural attractions that have not yet been exploited or promoted in a certain way.

Within the activities of implementation of the tourist circuit in the cantons Sucre and San Vicente stipulates a budget of \$ 2,850, which will be part of the performance of activities proposed and evaluated for the creation of the same, with the purpose of invigorating the tourist attractions of these cantons. Within the set of tourist attractions that make up the circuit according to preferences of tourists is shown in table 3.

Table 4: Ranking of attractions in Canton Sucre

Tourist attractions of Bahía de Caráquez and surrounding areas to Sucre Canton					
N°	Attractiveness name	Category	Type	Subtype	Hierarchy
1	Sector Historic Sites of Bahía C.	Cultural manifestations	Históricas	ArquitecturaLugaresHistóricos	III
2	Iglesia de La Merced	Cultural manifestations	Históricas	ArquitecturaReligiosa	III
3	Conjuntoparcial de casas antiguas de Charapotó	Cultural manifestations	Históricas	ArquitecturaLugaresHistóricos	II
4	Sitioarqueológico de Japotó	Cultural manifestations	Históricas	SitoArqueológico	III

5	Isla Fragata	Natural places	Costas	Refugio de vidasilvestre	II
6	Playa de Chirije	Natural places	Costas	Playas	II
7	Playa Pajonal	Natural places	Costas	Playas	I
8	Playa La Gorda, la Mesita, La Gringa, Bejuco, Punta bellaca, Playa Bellavista	Natural places	Costas	Línea de costa	II
9	Playa de Bahía	Natural places	Costas	Playas	II
10	Playa San Clemente	Natural places	Costas	Playas	II
11	Playa de San Jacinto	Natural places	Costas	Playas	II
12	Estuario del Río Chone	Natural places	Costas	Estuario	II
13	Reserva ecológica Cerro seco	Natural places	Bosques	Seco tropical	II
14	Bosque seco de Chirije	Natural places	Bosques	Seco tropical	II
15	Bosque la Gorda	Natural places	Bosques	Seco tropical	II
16	Red Bosque privado de la Cordillera del Bálsamo	Natural places	Bosques	Seco tropical	III
17	Río Grande	Natural places	Ríos	Ribera	II
Source: own elaboration with the following data (Ministry of Tourism of Ecuador, 2016)					

It is important to recognize that of these existing attractions all have hierarchical levels from I to III, where 23.5% of the attractions are ranked with level III, and 70.6% are attractive of level II and only 5.9% have hierarchy I. At the level of type of attractions of 8 denominations granted by the Ministry of Tourism of Ecuador only 4 are represented in the territory, of them 47.1% is represented by the denomination of coast, 25.5% by historical type and forests and 5.9% denominated by river . Reflecting that there is a tourist potential to develop the destination's offers.

Regarding the San Vicente canton, which is made up of three parishes, such as: San Vicente, Canoe and Briseño. Located on the coasts where its attractive potential are beaches, as shown in table 4.

Table 5: Ranking of attractions of the San Vicente canton

Nº	Attractiveness name	Category	type	Subtype	Hierarchy
1	Hacienda agrícola Río Muchacho	Cultural manifestatio ns	Manifestacionestécnicas y científicas	ExplotaciónAgropecuaria	III
2	Bebidastípicas-chichamaíz	Cultural manifestatio	Etnografía	Bebidastípicas	III

		ns			
3	Zona arqueológica Tabuchila	Cultural manifestatio ns	Históricas	Zona arqueológica	I
4	Alfarería Rosa Blanca de Briceño	Cultural manifestatio ns	Históricas	Artesanías	II
5	Zona arqueológica Rosa Blanca de Briceño	Cultural manifestatio ns	Históricas	Zona Arqueológica	II
6	Artesanías "Bejuco de Bajío" y "Madera Dura"	Cultural manifestatio ns	Manifestaciones artísticas contemporáneas	Artesanías	II
7	Zona arqueológica el Recreo	Cultural manifestatio ns	Históricas	Zona arqueológica	II
8	Recorrido de Eloy Alfaro o el Refugio de Alfaro	Cultural manifestatio ns	Históricas	Manifestaciones Religiosas, tradiciones y creencias populares, tradiciones y creencias	II
9	Playa los Perales	Natural places	Costas o Litorales	Playas	I
10	Playa San Vicente	Natural places	Costas o Litorales	Playas	II
11	Refugio de vida silvestre Isla Corazón	Natural places	Sistema de Áreas Protegidas	Refugio de vida silvestre	II
12	Playa Punta Napo	Natural places	Costas o Litorales	Playas	II
13	Playa de Briceño	Natural places	Costas o Litorales	Playas	II
14	Playa de Canoa	Natural places	Costas o Litorales	Playas	III
15	Cueva de los Murciélagos - Peñón de los Piqueros	Natural places	Fenómenos Espeleológicos	Cavernas	II
16	Playa Cabo Pasado	Natural places	Costas o Litorales	Playas	II

17	Bosque de Canoa	Natural places	Bosques	Húmedo Tropical Occidental	II
18	Bosque Cabo Pasado	Natural places	Bosques	Húmedo Tropical Occidental	II
Source: own elaboration with the following data (Ministry of Tourism of Ecuador, 2016)					

Of the attractions in the San Vicente canton, the most representative are 12 that represent the hierarchical level II, followed by the attractions of hierarchical level III and those of level I that represent 11.8% of the total attractions of the canton. Of these at the type level, the most representative are coastal or coastal areas representing 35.3%, followed by historic types with 29.4%, demonstrations and forests represent 11.8% and finally ethnography and protected area systems which represent 11.8%.

Dynamicmap of thetouristattractions of thecantons Sucre SanVicente, wherethecouristcircuit" THE CITY OF THE SUN "will be presented, isshownbelow as a circuitfordestinationmanagement.

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V. CONCLUSIONS:

The Kendall coefficient method allowed to determine the main problems exist for the management of the tourist destination, where $W = 0.94 \geq 0.5$, so the study of the coefficient of agreement turned out to be valid.

The diagnosis of hotel occupancy at the level of the cantons showed that there is infrastructure at the category level that supports the arrival of tourists in the area.

The existing attractions in the area are hierarchized at the category level, type and sub type that allows designing the circuit according to the tourist profile and corresponding recreational activities allowing a sustainable and competitive destination.

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